

Environment

July 2025

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The project POLICY ANSWERS monitors the implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda, and the broader context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this Monitoring Card, you find the results of the third round of data collection during 2024 and the first months of 2025 in comparison to the data collected in the previous second monitoring round.

In terms of Environment, the monitoring focuses on the “Regulatory Indicators for Sustainable Energy (RISE)” and various achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Regulatory Indicators for Sustainable Energy (RISE)

RISE is a framework that provides values for 23 indicators comparing policies and regulatory systems in support of sustainable energy. The evaluation is based on four key areas of sustainable energy: access to electricity, clean cooking, energy efficiency, and renewable energy.

Sources

Authors’ calculation based on RISE (2024) <https://rise.esmap.org/> (accessed 28 January 2025).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicators

Thematic soil pollution database for the Western Balkans		
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Western Balkans Economy Indicators

Indicator and overall assessment of the region	Western Balkans Green Agenda implemented			Counteracting climate change & environmental degradation		
	Transition to sustainable transport					
Albania	Only one public initiative in place, no new initiatives					
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Increased number of public initiatives					
Kosovo	One new public initiative in place					
Montenegro	No information provided					
North Macedonia	No public initiatives in the field					
Serbia	Increased number of public initiatives					

Legend: Information not available

Highlights

Western Balkans partners endorse Hamburg Declaration on the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans (GAWB)
Successful participation of the Western Balkans in the New European Bauhaus

